

Determination of auxotrophic nature of the mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₂₀₀ for improved L-lysine production

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Abstract : An experimental study was carried out to examine the auxotrophic nature of a newly developed mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₂₀₀. Yeast extract from the minimal salt medium was replaced by 0.1 µg/mL of biotin, to investigate the role of biotin on growth as well as production of L-lysine by this strain. Biotin (0.1 µg/mL) was proved to be an essential element for growth and production, however in excess amount a significant increase in cell growth lead to an anaerobic condition, which adversely affected L-lysine production.

Keywords : *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₂₀₀, yeast, biotin, L-lysine, auxotroph.

Introduction

L-Lysine is an essential amino acid produced via fermentation and is a key nutritional supplement for poultry and swine. More than forty different microorganisms have been demonstrated to biosynthesize L-lysine. On the commercial scale almost all production centers around the auxotrophic mutants of *Corynebacterium* (*Micrococcus*) *glutamicum* and *Bevibacterium* sp.^{1,2}.

A great variety of microorganism has been isolated or induced for amino acid production. They are classified into wild strain, auxotrophic mutants and regulatory mutant³. Among auxotrophic mutants derived from regulatory mutants of *Micrococcus glutamicus*, strains required biotin for their growth and L-lysine accumulation³.

These investigations were intended to examine the auxotrophic nature of the newly developed high L-lysine yielding strain of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₂₀₀.

Materials and methods :

Microorganism :

Micrococcus glutamicus AB₂₀₀ developed by induced mutation (using UV rays as physical mutagen and methyl methane sulfonate as chemical mutagen) in our laboratory was used throughout this study.

Basal salt medium for L-lysine production :

Basal salt medium contained glucose : 9%, urea : 0.2%, K₂HPO₄ : 0.1%, MgSO₄.7H₂O : 0.020%; yeast

extract : 0.2%; pH : 7.2.

Statistical analysis : Data were expressed as mean ± SEM, where n = 6. The data was analyzed by student's t test, by using MS Excel. Two measurements were considered significant if the corresponding *p* value < 0.05 (*) and considered highly significant if *p* < 0.01 (**).

Estimation of dry cell weight :

The cells were separated from the fermentation medium by filtration, washed with distilled water and filtered once again. The mass was dried in an oven at 100 °C for 24 h. It was then weighed to obtain the dry cell weight.

Analysis of amino acids :

Descending paper chromatography was employed for detecting L-lysine in culture medium and was run for 16 to 18 h on Whatman No. 1 chromatographic paper. Solvent system : n-butanol : acetic acid : water 2 : 1 : 1. The spots were visualized by spraying with a solution of 0.2% ninhydrine in acetone and quantitative estimation of L-lysine in the suspension was done using colorimetric estimation method.

Recovery and identification of L-lysine :

For the identification of L-lysine the fermentation broth after separation of cells was adjusted to pH 5 with HCl and filtered. The filtrate was then treated with active charcoal to remove the colored impurity. After filtration the

clear filtrate was finally passed through a Dowex 50 (H⁺ type) column in which the amino acid was absorbed. After washing with water and elution with 0.24 (N) HCl, the elute was further passed through an amberlite (H⁺ type) for elimination of chloride ion. The elute was concentrated by evaporation in vacuum and the product was obtained in a crystalline form in the cold. The pure material is proved to be L-lysine both by chemical test, optical rotation and by paper chromatographic method.

Insoluble picrate derivative of L-lysine was prepared and melting point of the derivative 266 °C⁴. Elemental analysis of the pure material gave the following values : C - 49.31%, H - 9.63%, N - 19.17%, O - 21.88%. Whereas the molecular calculation shows the following values : C - 49.29%, H - 9.65%, N - 19.16%, O - 21.89%.

The optical rotation was estimated as (L)_D²⁵ = 20.1 (C=2, 5 N HCl).

These data agreed with those of lysine.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 showed that production of L-lysine was maximum when yeast extract in the basal salt medium was replaced by 0.1 µg/mL biotin. When biotin concentration was increased above 0.1 µg/mL dry cell weight was increased significantly (*p* < 0.05) but production of L-lysine was decreased. When both 0.1% yeast extract and 0.1% biotin were simultaneously added to the medium, the production of L-lysine was decreased significantly (*p* < 0.05) along with significant increase (*p* < 0.01) of dry cell weight.

Fig. 1. Determination of auxotrophic nature of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₂₀₀. Data were expressed as mean ± SEM, n = 6. **p* < 0.05, ***p* < 0.01 when compared to control. (■) L-lysine (mg/mL), (■) dry cell weight (mg/mL).

Glutamic acid producing bacteria require biotin for growth and its concentration must be strictly controlled for the maximum yield of L-lysine⁵. Young and Chipley

(1984) investigated the role of biotin in L-lysine production in *Brevibacterium lactofermentum* and found that biotin treated cell took up more glucose, than did the control one⁶. Shah *et al.* (2002) studied the effect of biotin on the bacterial fermentation of L-lysine and reported that best production was obtained at (5 µg/100 mL) 0.05 µg/mL of biotin concentration. The cell mass increased upto 0.20 µg/mL of biotin and then remains constant^{7,10}.

Biotin, apparently, caused some compositional changes in the cell wall membrane complex, allowing an increase in uptake of glucose. The result of uptake studies and fatty acid analysis suggested that biotin affects the cell surface, probably the bacterial membrane. It is well known that bacterial membrane plays an important role as a charged barrier. This mechanism might also regulate the amount of L-lysine released by the cell. Tosaka *et al.* (1979) suggested that the effect might be due to the activation of pyruvate carboxylase by biotin⁸. Shio *et al.* (1962) studied the effect of biotin on the bacterial cells increased tremendously leading to creation of anaerobic state⁹.

Our present study also support the above mentioned trend. Yeast extract is a complex nutrient which may also contain biotin. The production of L-lysine might be decreased due to the presence of excess biotin both yeast extract (0.1 µg/mL) and biotin (0.1 µg/mL) were added in the broth. So from the present investigation it was tentatively concluded that the mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₂₀₀ was a biotin requiring auxotroph and its maximum production of L-lysine can be obtained in presence of 0.1 µg/mL biotin in the present condition of fermentation.

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